

Municipal Tech Regime: Jokowi and Patrimonial Internet Techno-Politics in Post-Soeharto, Indonesia

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Abstract

During the New Order era under Suharto, the government built an electricity system for rural communities, including generators and television with broadcasts of national specials. These people welcomed the gates of a better life and entertainment with open arms-and were indirectly moved to vote for the Golkar Party. The fall of Suharto in the reform era triggered the emergence of petty kings such as mayors and city governments. Internet technology in the city of Semarang and its concept as a smart city is one example where the mayor gets political support, expertise, and funds from the central government to carry out the personal interests of the Indonesian government and the city government. The mayor followed Suharto's patrimonial techno-political pattern from a decentralized perspective, although there were still many differences between regimes. While centralized techno-political regimes focus on the supreme leader, decentralized techno-politics pay more attention to society and its stakeholders. Therefore, a technological regime in Post-Suharto Indonesia requires special characteristics and great efforts to be able to implement a decentralized techno-politics that can communicate and foster trust among its people.

Keywords: *Indonesia, Techno-Political, Techno-Political Regime, Municipality, Mayor, ICT, Smart City.*

INTRODUCTION

Modern technology is the Swiss Army knife with multiple blades – which can be used by the central government and lower authorities for their specific purposes. Our history has written about nuclear power as a techno-political vehicle, the strategy of which involves the use of certain technologies to set political goals (Hecht 2009, p. 56). Even electricity, which is not necessarily nuclear power, has some form of political power in the grid. The Suharto government, one of the longest-serving governments in Southeast Asia, utilized electricity and television to not only assist rural residents in remote areas, but also to foster political voice through patrimonial techno-politics (Mohsin 2014, p. 68). Information and Communication Technology (ICT), linked by the internet, has emerged for decades as a tool of today's government (Gagliardini 2018, p. 270).

However, the internet is not a universal panacea that can solve every problem facing governments. The Internet is simply a platform where conflict occurs (Kellner 2001, Rasmussen 2007). Its open nature has allowed the wider population to participate freely in it, but this can also lead to chaos. The urgent question we must ask is whether governments are exploiting the internet and having dangerous consequences. The head of government will not be the dominant force of the government itself, or of society. A strong government will rule while a weak government tries to rule, distributing its authority to others. This article draws on the government's techno-politics to investigate the establishment of internet regimes by municipal governments in Indonesia, with a focus on Semarang City, Central Java.

In addition, this article will examine the development of this regime initiated by the mayor who uses ICT and the inclusive concept of smart cities to govern society. The city of Semarang is a leading pilot project of the Indonesian government's smart city scheme. This article will mostly present a comparison between the techno-politics of the centralized Suharto era and the decentralized post-Soeharto era. While Suharto used television as a tool to build a techno-political regime, the current government uses ICT, both of which are driven by electricity.

The analysis of previous research can be divided according to the position of technology towards the media, as well as whether the technology is the internet. Research by Kellner (2001), Rasmussen (2007), Gagliardone and Golooba-Mutebi (2016), and Gagliardone (2018) focuses on the internet and the blurring of boundaries between technology and media. The mention of technology as a medium is based on McLuhan's ideas (Cooper, 2015). The internet has become a technology as well as a medium that must be managed by implementing strategies and tactics to seize power. The research of Urtasun, Luquin, and Garrido (2017) becomes research on the internet, but separates technology and media, contrary to McLuhan's argument. The research of Urtasun and colleagues describes technopolitics from a historical perspective; the internet only emerged after the authoritarian era ended, namely in the era of democracy. The historical

perspective shows that the internet is one of the media supporting the regime. Media has its own function, as well as regime technology has its own function, for example nuclear.

This article will use Hecht's (2009) techno-political theory, which also examines techno-political beliefs and techno-political regimes. The patrimonial techno-political concept proposed by Mohsin (2014) has also been considered. These two concepts will help answer two important research questions about how and why a mayor uses internet techno-politics. In addition, one must bear in mind the paradoxical nature of the internet, as it can have both positive and negative impacts.

When a mayor decides to utilize ICT in his programmes, the reasons and strategies must first be identified for implementing it. The first part of this article will describe the techno-politics of the mayor of Semarang City, while the second part will discuss the reasons behind this technology decision. The study was also based on semi-structured interviews which featured a pre-prepared list of questions as a structural blueprint, but also allowed for open-ended questions. As the recent pandemic situation has enforced social distancing protocols that the researchers in this study respected with respondents, interviews were conducted using online messaging and email platforms. Respondents who agreed to participate in the study would then confirm the interview they wished to attend, either by email or cell phone.

METHOD

This research uses a case study by selecting one case that includes individuals and cultural groups. The researcher begins the research by identifying cases that are in the form of a system and are bound by time and place (Kusmarni, 2012).

Types and sources of data are divided into two, primary and secondary data (Strauss & Corbin, 1990). The researcher conducted a pre-research since May 6, 2017 when attending a public discussion of Tangguh Semarang in the Old City of Semarang. The discussion resulted in initial data about the crucial problems faced by the city of Semarang.

Data analysis and data interpretation were based on Creswell (2009). The process starts from the collection of all raw data. The researcher saved the interview data in the form of a transcript and put it in the same folder as the other data. The second process is data management and preparation for analysis after tidying up all raw data. The third process is the process of reading all the data owned. The researcher reads over and over again each data, understands, and looks for relevance to this research. There is a lot of raw data, but not all data can be included in the study. The fourth process is the reduction process, researchers identify or select data, classification, and coding.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Techno-Political President of Indonesia

There is a lot of literature stating that the New Order regime prioritized technocrats, but it cannot be denied that the Old Order regime under Soekarno had built a technology system in the health sector. Due to the destruction and injuries caused by the war against Japanese and Dutch colonialism, health technology became a priority for the people of post-colonial Indonesia. Diseases such as malaria, tuberculosis, yaws and leprosy are sweeping across the nation at an alarming rate. During this period, doctors were widely regarded as technocrats who helped find solutions for society to avoid dependence on Western technology (Neelakantan, 2014). In addition, the tensions between countries that emerged after World War II gave Sukarno the belief that Indonesia should achieve technological independence, rather than relying on other countries.

Suharto is known for his success in realizing the electrification of Indonesian villages throughout his regime, which stems from Soekarno's vision. Suharto aspired that the electrification project would benefit the welfare of many people, even though it required a large budget and inevitably caused political overtones. Moreover, Suharto and his political parties took advantage of this momentum to gain votes in the general election (Mohsin, 2014). Suharto, who was very obsessed with Western technology, carried out aircraft techno-politics with Bacharuddin Jusuf Habibie, a German graduate, regime technocrat and Suharto's successor as Indonesia's third president (Amir, 2007). Suharto also entrusted Habibie to develop nuclear technology while he was a minister. However, the development of nuclear electrification at Muria, delayed by Habibie's ambitious aircraft budget, ultimately failed due to the fall of Suharto (Amir, 2010). His role as a New Order technocrat and political supporter of Suharto did not give Habibie much political power as president, especially since Suharto was hereditary from the presidential role. The weakness of Habibie's presidential leadership also led to the East Timor referendum (Amir, 2007) and with the fall of Suharto, this further proved the importance of political power in carrying out techno-politics.

The reform period opened the political scene for the fourth president, Abdurrahman Wahid, who was considered a mediator between various groups, especially the Muslim and secular population. Wahid formed a national leadership based on compassion and tolerance, prioritizing inter-community harmony by considering modern science and technology

as a useless means of solving problems, or even having a negative impact on society (Rochmat, 2017). Wahid's rejection of nuclear technology ended when he finally collaborated with the global nuclear agency at the end of his governorship. Megawati Soekarnoputri, Indonesia's fifth president and Soekarno's daughter, signed a cooperation agreement with Russia on nuclear development. This nuclear study recommends the Muria area, which is home to the traditional Islamic community of Jepara, as the main location for building a nuclear reactor. Meanwhile, resistance to traditional Islamic societies began in the mid-1990s and grew stronger after the fall of Suharto. Decentralization eventually gave birth to civil society that actively influences local development and decisions (Fauzan & Schiller, 2011).

Interest and discourse on the construction of nuclear facilities in the Muria area re-emerged when the sixth president, Susilo Bambang Yudhoyono, took over his role. At that time, Yudhoyono was working with South Korea in the field of nuclear technology. However, nuclear techno-politics faced opposition from the local community, thus hampering the discourse. The government had proposed relocating nuclear facilities, one of which was explained by the fourth president, Wahid, but this project was delayed until the term of the seventh president, Joko Widodo (Jokowi) (Amir, 2010). Broadly speaking, Indonesia has sought technological independence at the beginning of its independence due to the global political constellation at that time. The application of technology in the New Order regime really depended on the government leadership and its technocrats. Suharto's downfall and decentralization have made it very difficult for the government to steer the country's techno-politics due to the involvement of key stakeholders in important decision-making. Jokowi is also faced with a similar problem, forcing the government to choose other forms of technology, such as the Internet, over nuclear because it does not conspire against the aspirations of the people. Therefore, Jokowi runs techno-politics by involving the city government and ICT. One interesting case that deserves further investigation is the Semarang City Government led by Mayor Hendrar Prihadi. The city of Semarang is one of the pilot projects of the national smart city movement run by the Jokowi government.

The Embryo of Mayor Techno-Politics

The Mayor of Semarang, Hendrar Prihadi, took office in 2012 as an executor after two years serving as deputy mayor who was previously dismissed. Hendrar won elections in 2015 to be re-elected mayor for another five years, and this article will consider eight years of his appointment as the study limit. Nana Storada Dwi Martadi, the mayor's expert-staff and former high-ranking official at the local government's communications and informatics office, explained that the city government had started using ICT for the first time in 2005. Hendrar's government initiated an ICT program in 2013 by installing 2,300 free internet hotspots on site. general.¹ The mayor's development of a public internet network can also be considered as a techno-political tool, unlike what Suharto did using electricity (Mohsin 2014, p. 85). The public internet service is a form of giving the mayor to be grateful for by the community.

However, the Hendrar government has installed a public internet network without full awareness of the complex vision of the smart city concept. Arif Budiman, an official with the local government's communications and informatics office, stated that the mayor was not aware of the smart city concept until national officials, as well as other city governments, informed him. In addition, the high level of use of ICT in the city brings Semarang in Indonesia's e-Government ranking. The mayor then received conceptual support from a senior academic and engineer from the Bandung Institute of Technology (ITB), Suhono Harso Supangkat. In a recent conversation, the professor revealed to us that he has been conducting ongoing research, discussion, review and consultation in Semarang since 2015.² Apart from ITB, the mayor is seeking assistance from various leading local universities and polytechnics as an important political design strategy. ITB's participation in particular in Semarang's techno-politics became a repetition of Suharto's electricity program when the New Order involved Sutami, a technocrat across regimes since Soekarno's Old Order who holds a bachelor's degree from ITB but is a lecturer at the University of Indonesia (UI). Suharto invited Sutami to join his cabinet and head the Department of Public Works and Electricity, while Suhono remained as a contributor working separately outside the government system (Mohsin, 2014).

Decentralization and Patrimonial

techno-politics Indonesia has become a decentralized country, therefore any discussion about the mayor's techno-politics may be related to the techno-politics of the Indonesian president, Jokowi. Hendrar and Jokowi are from the same political party, *the Indonesian Democratic Party of Struggle* (PDIP). The Jokowi administration initiated the national smart city movement in 2017, choosing Semarang as one of its pilot projects.³ The government provided funding and mentoring for all selected cities, including Semarang.⁴ This political patronage between the central government and the municipality parallels Suharto's techno-politics. The top-to-bottom movement involves experts proposed by the central government. One of these experts is Adi Mulyanto, an academic and technocrat from ITB, who helped draft the Semarang smart city vision master plan. In formulating the master plan, Adi interviewed the mayor to gain a comprehensive understanding of his vision, mission and objectives.⁵

The Jokowi administration then instructed these selected smart cities to form large-scale stakeholder engagement councils, prompting the Mayor of Semarang to invite local stakeholders to join his councils. The council itself is the

foundation of various collaborative actions to realize a smart city, starting with the formulation of a master plan. One can compare smart city councils to the French nuclear energy commission described by Hecht (2009). When former French President Charles de Gaulle came to power, he formed a nuclear development council. Some similarities also lie when former Indonesian President Suharto formed the power and electricity agency as a techno-political embryo of the New Order (Mohsin, 2014). Jokowi reflected his central government's policy towards cities by creating city-based institutions, while de Gaulle and Suharto directly built national institutions.

While the Mayor of Semarang is an extension of the president, he maintains a special interest. The mayor applies a co-creation process that includes creative, dynamic and social aspects in developing innovative services through interactive collaboration between the government and stakeholders. Co-creation can have emotional outcomes (affective commitment), rational outcomes (trust), and behavioral outcomes (loyalty) (Iglesias et al., 2020). Many political candidates are driven to build their political brand by growing public trust to win the election. Trust is essential in Indonesian democracy, a country where corruption was once rampant. People may accept the vulnerability of politicians they trust as a sign of good intentions and behavior (Susila et al., 2019). Therefore, if the mayor participates in creating a techno-political institution, he must seek the trust and voice of the people. In one of his interviews, Hendrar admitted that the restoration of the bureaucracy was not only a manifestation of his commitment to Semarang, but also an effort to gain public trust.

Semarang City Regime

Techno-political Co-creation and the creation of institutions by Jokowi and Suharto are just a few signs of the manifestation of the techno-political regime, which itself refers to a regime based on an institution, a concept initiated by Hecht (2009). It combines people, industrial techniques and practices, technological artifacts, political programs and institutional ideologies. The collaborative institution will then deploy technology to actualize techno-politics. In this regard, the Mayor of Semarang, Hendrar Prihadi, is the main initiator of the current regime, where his assessment is an important foundation for his techno-political grand design. The mayor consolidates the system using formal and informal communications. After the mayor, the next regime member is an official from the local government's communications and information service. This department is responsible for providing support and consulting, developing ICT, media management, data collection, and data integration. Then came officials from the local government development department. This department will use the data to formulate the Plan *Regional Medium-Term Development (RPJMD)*, which is a political promise between the mayor and the people, and synchronizes the interests of both parties. The final regime members are officials from other local government agencies, all of whom must demonstrate their commitment to joining this collaborative regime. Signatures were then collected as a form of commitment to strengthen government cooperation.

The regime also requires the involvement of technocrats and practitioners. Technocrats from ITB and other universities act as these techno-political think tanks. In addition to ITB, the regime made a memorandum of understanding (MoU) and invited students from the local technology university, Dian Nuswantoro University (UDINUS). Arif revealed, around 300 students underwent internships for three months at government agencies in Semarang.⁷ This regime is realized through the work of SOEs such as Telkom Indonesia, state-owned banks and PLN. The regime also allows contributions from regionally owned enterprises. While Suharto's electricity techno-politics prioritized PLN as the main technology enabler, the mayor's internet techno-politics sided with Telkom and appointed PLN as a supporting institution. The regime also welcomes the involvement of privately owned companies, including small and medium enterprises (SMEs).

As the government had to spread the message of development to the people, mass media companies were listed as important stakeholders to help build the regime, which also began to cultivate thriving relationships with many social media influencers. In addition, the regime runs public relations activities and government social media accounts to communicate with mass media companies and social media influencers. Through it, the regime gains a certain level of access and connectedness with various contemporary communities. Institutions and co-working spaces have also been established to help bring the whole community together. The people of Semarang themselves are the last target of stakeholders, as well as a crucial techno-political actor. Therefore, the regime carries out its commitment to the welfare of the people by building free internet access in public facilities.

The Semarang city government has also deployed several technological instruments, with free public internet access as the first in a series of exclusive initiatives by the mayor. This includes various online applications and software to support public services, such as the government website (*Semarangkota.go.id*) which provides official information and important data. Meanwhile, social media platforms have been used to communicate with the wider population. Other tools include smart cards, brought in through collaborative projects with private stakeholders. Certain technology providers agree to print these cards for free to ease some of the burden on the government budget, which also provides them with some economic benefits. During the coronavirus pandemic, mayors were forced to apply digital signatures and teleconferencing at various institutions as an effort to prevent the spread of the virus. Semarang's big data system includes a series of Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV), social media analytics, big data analytics and command center.

While the regime has taken advantage of all these technological artifacts, they are being implemented in stages. The government only modifies some existing artifacts, such as government websites, while others like smart cards and big data are technological innovations that should be pushed into the public eye. To further shed light on the issue of government websites, it has been in development since the early 2000s but requires further streamlining and redesign to accommodate the data output of integrated big data systems. The regime finally created a unique subdomain of the government website called "*Semarang Smart City*", where the content is supplied from big data analytics. The data is categorized into six conceptual dimensions, including intelligence in governance, branding, economy, life, society and the environment. Hexa-smartness is a political program that has been designed, and its message is intended to be distributed through websites and social media.

In addition, the technological artifacts used by the techno-political regime of Semarang are not only internet networks. The mayor continues and gradually introduces more technological artifacts, or tools, that will help the construction of smart cities. There are many technological artifacts that the mayor gradually introduces. There are fundamental differences that distinguish him from Suharto's techno-politics which tend to involve more superficial technological artifacts. The techno-electric policy, for example, only provides electricity generators for disadvantaged villages, where the generators are then used to turn on television for local people to get information and entertainment. Not surprisingly, the government-provided television featured only one state station. However, the precious presence of television reinforced Suharto's patrimonial techno-politics (Mohsin, 2014). This shows how techno-politics in the Suharto era favored a top-down approach. On the other hand, techno-politics by utilizing the internet network is also open to public aspirations, which provides room for a bottom-up approach. Even though he is wearing a democratic suit, you can still see the presence of patrimonial techno-politics, although in a slightly different form. The techno-political patrimony in Semarang City can be seen especially in the internet network and information management.

Intelligence is the most important ideology of the city's techno-political regime. Adi discusses the ideology of intelligence, the foundation of which is none other than computational thinking. Therefore, intelligent thinking leads to logical thinking, and outcomes that are useful in decision making. Computational thinkers can often find the best solutions through computers and data.⁸ It is very important that all stakeholders of the regime have the same way of thinking. On this basis, Bunyamin, a high-ranking official at the local government development agency, emphasized how intelligence is paramount in sustainable urban improvement, which is aimed at economic growth, maximizing human resources, and reducing poverty. This will then allow the smart regime to pave the way to the city's prosperity. Another ideology that is no less important is mutual cooperation necessary between the various pillars of government, private sector, universities, mass media, community, and society. This is where adopting an egalitarian approach can be beneficial, as it will enable effective collaboration and constructive collaboration.

Moreover, these different pillars of the regime are more likely to come together with trust.⁹ Compared to Suharto's techno-political regime, previous political tactics did not require participants to be smart. The public is expected to be passive, accepting government gifts and subsidies without asking too many questions in return for their vote in the next general election. In addition, television broadcasts have indirectly shaped the public into passive recipients of government messages. Even the ideology of gotong royong is not needed, because society remains passive collectively.

Trust and the Moving Regime

Trust plays an important role in changing techno-political regimes by engaging people, industrial techniques and practices, technological artifacts, political programs, and institutional ideologies. While a complex chain of command can become useless without cooperation, trust allows all components to move together. In this regard, the mayor becomes an important aspect in building trust among cross-stakeholder collaboration in this techno-political regime. The greater the command or order, the more deeply rooted the people's trust must be in the mayor. As the center of his government, the mayor needs to win the trust of stakeholders in the direction and vision of the regime. Before speaking with any of the individual stakeholders, we should focus on how mayor's build relationships between individuals. Adi explained that mayors often take advantage of formal government events to discuss and elaborate on their vision, mission, and goals. Formal communication is carried out during formal events such as briefing meetings, internal monitoring and evaluation of the city government, socialization and public discussions. Policies will generate more authority and more respect if they are formally communicated.

However, the mayor's formal explanation is often followed by informal conversations with certain individuals. This allows the mayor to build a closer relationship with the people, especially when he approaches them as a friendly face, rather than a distant political leader. Therefore, the right combination of formal and informal communication has proven to be effective in helping mayors achieve their results. The Mayor of Semarang himself is known for his naturally charismatic figure, as evidenced by Suhono, and has the ability to communicate with anyone in a friendly manner. When he spoke, he was always calm, composed and almost never angry. The mayor's pleasant communication style makes it easy for the public to receive him with warmth everywhere.¹¹

Awareness of utilizing formal and informal communication will help stakeholders, namely the community, to provide support for technology. Gerry Firmansyah, a high-ranking official from a government agency established to encourage the development of ICT in Indonesia, explained the importance of this awareness so that government information does not appear to come from the government itself. There is a tendency among the public to reject any information provided by the government, while messages that are gently wrapped have a greater chance of being received. When the public trusts the goodwill of the government and tolerates its flaws, they will understand the functionality and support the technology provided to them. People who are aware can undermine the technology provided by the government. It provides public support for the implementation of the regime's political program.

The trust and awareness that has been formed will create a closer relationship between stakeholders. The mayor can exert influence on each of the stakeholders in the techno political regime. Meanwhile, shared trust will facilitate collaborative action that requires all components of the regime to act together. The joint movement requires commitment from stakeholders, one of which is in the form of a formal institution called a smart city council. The smart city council is made up of all parties involved in the smart city program, which will then form the basis for implementing smart cities until 2030 – this will continue despite the change of mayor due to elections. Another strategy to ensure smooth collective action is through the signing of an MoU. The difference is that the smart city council will become a giant umbrella in implementing smart city programs, while the MoU will become a bridge between certain programs and the involvement of certain parties. One could argue that commitment is a form of alignment of agreed direction and goals.

Commitment requires accountability, and this requires the mayor to explain the results of the commitment to the regime, including the mandate to facilitate stakeholder aspirations. The results obtained in each component of the technopolitical regime can be either success or failure, while accountability is the evaluation of these results. The mayor must ensure that everyone involved in the regime has commitment, responsibility, clarity of roles, conformity with their fields and appropriate work results. Therefore, the leadership of the mayor can determine whether a stable techno political regime will materialize. Adi explained that the Mayor of Semarang has a clear goal and provides direction to the community to work towards that goal. He is able to change the vision, mission, and goals of his regime in a direction that is easily understood by the human resources who will work with him. It will be difficult to implement any vision without clear instructions for subordinates to follow. Therefore, a mayor must understand the direction of a regime and the actions that need to be taken. Thus, mayoral leadership involves monitoring, controlling, and reminding the team when certain goals or outcomes are not as desired.¹³ Leaders of techno political regimes need to collaborate with all their stakeholders and participants, and not everyone has the right attitude or personality for this.

Reasons behind Techno-politics

Suharto's techno-techno-politics are not the same as Jokowi's and Hendrar's. Suharto, when he came to power in 1966, formulated an electrification program to improve the lives of villagers and their economic activities. It guarantees national stability through techno-politics by encouraging economic growth and equitable distribution of development benefits (Mohsin 2014, p. 64). Suharto's techno-political politics involved creating demands for his goals. Meanwhile, Arif explained that the three aspects behind Hendrar's techno-political decisions were the progress of society, the demands of the community, and the demands of the wider environment.¹⁴ The mayor's techno politics was at one point a decision that reflected dependence on the surrounding environment. However, the government seems to have no choice and is forced to use internet technology. It must be understood that internet-based techno-politics is not an easy matter for every regional head to handle, because each has their own way of managing technology.

In this case, the Mayor of Semarang understands that the proper use of the internet can help him realize several interests at once. There are five political interests of the mayor in carrying out techno-politics. The first political interest is bureaucratic reform. In an interview, the mayor of Semarang explained how people in the city used to criticize the government for working too slowly, spending illegal fees and other unpleasant things. The public's perspective on government is very broad. The mayor wants to simplify the bureaucracy which, according to him, hinders public services in government affairs. Technology can be used to improve public services. The importance of bureaucratic reform is related to trust, which is the driving dynamo in techno-politics.¹⁵ Trust in politics can even be a winning factor in elections (Susila et al., 2019), where political victory is often the hidden and hidden goal of every politician.

The two mayors' political interests are solving urban problems. A metropolitan city is almost always faced with problems such as slum settlements, poverty and unemployment. When a community elects a leader, they are given the responsibility to find a solution to this problem. Techno-politics are expected to contribute to the process of solving urban problems. The community will surely remember and respect the local leaders who are actively working on this issue. The current situation with Covid-19 has strengthened the political interest in solving urban problems. Technology is often the solution, especially during times of unprecedented pandemics. Many new programs were launched, including the online shopping application Tumbasin, where people can buy household necessities without having to physically visit traditional markets. Limitation of human contact is necessary to reduce transmission of the virus.

The political interest of the three mayors is participation in the central government's political program, which in this context is the Jokowi administration. The mayor explained his relationship with the president in an interview, making it clear that he did not stand alone as mayor, but with help from the governor and president.¹⁶ It is no coincidence that the mayor, governor, and president belong to the same party, PDI-P. However, it should be noted that Jusuf Kalla, Jokowi's vice president at the start of this national smart city techno-politics, came from the Golkar Party, the party supported by Suharto. Mayors can benefit from this central government program by winning national votes. Political and financial support will assist the mayor in carrying out the city's techno-politics.

The fourth political interest is media coverage at the national level. News covering the city has a huge impact on the image of the head of government. The success of urban planning management, especially through prestigious awards and recognitions, is very beneficial for the mayor because it has interesting news value, as explained by Wahyu Aji, CEO of online media who is known for spreading optimistic accounts about Indonesia, including Semarang. Aji explained that Semarang was followed by Jakarta, Bandung and Surabaya as the most successful cities in finding solutions and improving public services. This success will never be recognized by the community without a proactive attitude from the government. City governments need to manage the media, build relationships with media owners and carry out various public relations functions.¹⁷ Successfully targeting certain news awards and values, supported by effective media handling and public relations, is an appropriate strategy to increase public trust in the mayor.

Finally, the fifth mayor's political interest is political propaganda. Mayor Hendrar has a political slogan, "*Semarang Great*," which symbolizes the city's pride and superiority over other cities in Indonesia. The slogan is also an acronym that denotes some of the main goals of the government. Hendrar's administration focuses on Health, Education, Building infrastructure, Attitudes and behavior and Trade (HEBAT).

Every techno-political regime has a compelling reason to build one. Not only is a regime dependent on its leader, but most of them share the same point of view on technology. Hecht identifies two lines of thought behind the choice of certain technologies, namely the interests of national identity and economic benefits. If a regime is concerned with national identity, then there is a possibility that alternative regimes will offer economic benefits. National identity belongs to regimes that control technology independently, although they may not be as effective and efficient. In addition, leaders who prioritize pride and independence often make national identity the main driver. On the other hand, economic benefits can also be obtained by obtaining technology from other parties, which the government sometimes responds to to carry out techno-politics. Even so, the economic benefits obtained are very high (Hecht, 2009). Techno-political regimes often have to choose one approach: political or economic.

Analyzing the city of Semarang, we can recognize how the city's techno political regime considers political and economic approaches. The case in France that Hecht studied shows two major regimes in the political contest of nuclear techno. Meanwhile, the case in Indonesia during the Suharto era underlined the New Order regime by completely ignoring alternative regimes. However, previous research stated that the previous regime, namely Soekarno, also saw electrification (Mohsin, 2014). The case of the city of Semarang is unique because Hendrar started with more sophisticated techno-politics than his predecessor, which only applied simple internet network technology, while Hendrar developed a more complex big data system.

On the other hand, the political approach can be realized by mastering technology independently. Arif explained that government service applications, one of the technological artifacts discussed earlier in this article, were developed in two different ways: in-house and by third parties. The internal human resources of the city government have developed some applications, while others have been outsourced to external programmers. Although some applications have been developed by outsiders, the city government retains the management rights. With some professional advice from academics, all the applications developed internally and externally can then be unified under one command center, which is another artifact built by the city government. This is the control system used by the mayor to understand the integrated data and help him make decisions. It is built with a modified liquid crystal display (LCD) TV connected to other equipment.¹⁸ In addition, the mayor also forced all levels of government to study ICT, while personally pleading with those who refused to resign. This shows how much the mayor demands technological mastery from the regime, despite the necessary dependence on other parties.

This technology outsourcing system is quite common. Suhono explained that the government focuses on providing services; development is the task of industry. Thus, the government's role is to build a regime with stakeholders who can contribute to the regime's goals. Compared to the nuclear techno political regime in France, which separated the two regimes according to their approach, the Semarang case was not yet at the end of the political pendulum. Then if analyzed based on an economic approach, the techno political regime of Semarang City is very economical.

This approach is supported by the mayor's efforts to win over the national smart city movement in 2017. ICT is an expensive technology, although funding from the central government has helped a lot to implement it. According to Arif, the city government must save budget, unlike big cities like Bandung which also run smart cities – the difference in budget

is equal to 1:20. Budget savings from Semarang are also important for the smooth running of the smart city national movement. This strengthens the belief of this article that the regime in Semarang prioritizes an economic approach, with a slight touch of a political approach.

Bunyamin also said that the government is working with state-owned banks, for example, to make smart cards that can be used to access bus rapid transit services. Banks make smart cards with municipal government labels, so that the municipal government budget can be reduced to a minimum, even to zero percent. Smart city technology must be realized because it must be adjusted to the government's economic capacity. Adi explained, technology for smart cities can still be realized even with limited resources, if maximized and optimized. Again, finding smart solutions requires a smart mindset. Moreover, the ideal concept for a smart city is one that does not overwhelm the budget. Semarang's techno-political regime is a good example. On the other hand, Suharto's techno political regime had to take a political approach because the budget was not taken into account in its action plans. Thus, the government provides technology that people may not ask for (Mohsin, 2014).

CONCLUSION

Indonesia's reforms shifted from a centralized government to a decentralized one after the fall of the New Order, which allowed for an increase in the role of local government. President Soeharto's electrified techno political regime and Mayor Hendrar's internet techno political regime, with the support of President Jokowi, are two cases that can be used to compare two different eras. President Soeharto started his leadership with the broad concept of national development, which explicitly mentioned electrification and state television as political programs to be implemented. Meanwhile, Mayor Hendrar started his administration by building a public internet and new media network to develop a big data analytics system as a new medium for decision making. Hendrar's ICT utilization has also reached a higher level, thanks to the help of the central government and the national smart city program.

Both Suharto and Hendrar's technological decisions stemmed from their roles as heads of government. The difference is, Hendrar can synchronize his technology decisions with the government above him, namely the central government, in the smart city program. Both have the support of technocrats affiliated with leading national technology institutes, while academics act as think tanks for their techno political regime. Moreover, Suharto is from the Golkar Party, while Hendrar and Jokowi are politicians from the PDI-P. Hendrar is a PDIP cadre who is considered capable of synchronizing his technological decisions with the central government. The central government also supports its technical political program through external political support, expertise and funding.

The Soeharto & Hendrar regimes both developed institutions that could be used as the basis for carrying out techno-politics. While centralized institutions tend to adopt a top-down approach, decentralized institutions involve co-creation from the ground up. Mayors use a co-creation approach to deliver innovative services through government and multi-stakeholder collaboration. Co-creation can also generate trust and loyalty – two things that politicians need most in an era of democracy. Suharto's techno-political regime only involved SOEs and the media, universities and sub-district governments. Technological artifacts also tend to be simpler, such as electricity generators and televisions. On the other hand, Hendrar's techno-political regime involves more stakeholders, including local governments, universities, state and local government-owned companies, private companies, mass media, social media influencers, urban communities and communities. The artifacts themselves are more complex, such as public internet networks, government websites, social media, smart cards, digital signatures, teleconferencing, big data and social media analytics, CCTV, and command centers. This diverse technology is also possible given the rapid development of technology over time.

The ideology upheld by the Hendrar regime is smartness, which is related to computational thinking and the values of a holistic approach in addition to maximizing human resources. An intelligent regime, one might say, will lead us to prosperity. Another ideology used is cooperation, which involves bringing together various pillars towards a common goal. Stakeholders in the regime can only cooperate only if there is trust.

On the other hand, the ideology of the Suharto regime does not require the people to be intelligent, because it relies on the people's passive attitude and public obedience. Trust is the prime mover of techno-politics. Mayors must build trust through formal and informal communication so that the techno-political regime can move together under the same vision, mission and goals. Formal communication, for example, is carried out through official government programs and has a more solid and reliable formal foundation. Informal communication can serve to strengthen friendly relations and clarify formal communication. Mayors also have personal characteristics that are important in building trust. Mayors tend to be enthusiastic, calm, rarely angry and can bring closer communication with the community. Communication is geared towards building awareness, thereby making technology more accessible to stakeholders. Trust and awareness build close relationships with all stakeholders. This close relationship also resulted in a shared commitment to move the regime. Commitment requires accountability because every stakeholder needs consideration of their successes and failures. In

essence, the mayor must translate the vision, mission, and goals to the level of education below him. Vision tends to be abstract; every member of the regime tends to have difficulty translating it.

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There are also different reasons behind the techno-politics of the Suharto and Hendrar regimes. Suharto carried out techno-politics to increase the distribution of people's welfare which had an impact on national stability, and decision-making and creation of needs. Meanwhile, Hendrar runs techno-politics because it has become a necessity due to advances in modern technology. Community progress, community needs, and wider environmental needs are the three driving points that underlie Hendrar's decision. The development of the internet is something that every regional head must anticipate, regardless of the challenges that accompany it. Hendrar Kepentingan It started with bureaucratic reform, which aimed to change the public's perception of the government from distrust and skepticism to belief.

Hendrar's second interest is to find solutions to various urban problems faced by metropolitan cities such as Semarang, including slum settlements, poverty and unemployment. The pandemic situation shows the importance of solving problems as the virus forces the government to remain productive despite having to reduce face-to-face meetings and functions. The third political interest is participation in the central government's political program. Mayors rely on political support, expertise and funding from the central government. Incidentally the mayor and president are from the same party. The fourth interest is media coverage at the national level. The City Government's success in obtaining newsworthy awards resulted in positive media coverage. The fifth and final interest is the main propaganda through the slogan "Semarang Great", which legitimizes any changes that occur in the city because of the role of Mayor Hendrar.

There are two reasons for choosing technology in techno political regimes: politically nuanced national identity and economic benefits. The case in Semarang shows a tendency towards economic gain, although it does not ignore the political aspect either. The city regime attempted to tighten its budget by establishing an efficient techno-political system. Smart city technology enables budget savings, even zero budget. Semarang City budget can save 1:20 compared to other cities; This makes the city of Semarang able to win the national assessment. The city government is also trying to develop its own technology, although it still needs the help of a third party. Furthermore, the mayor emphasized that all government employees are fluent in ICT. These efforts demonstrate the political and economic aspects of the city regime. While Suharto's techno-political regime focused on pure politics and did not think about the budget, Hendrar's regime has considered economic and political aspects. The success of a program can lead to a public voice supporting it, and *vice versa*.

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